

Poesia Cinética

O Caso da Censura a *Roda Lume* de E. M. de Melo e Castro

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E. M. de Melo e Castro, *Lírica do objecto*, filme 8 mm, p/b, sem som, 3'12", 1958.

Fonte: Arquivo Digital da PO.EX. <https://po-ex.net/taxonomia/materialidades/videograficas/e-m-de-melocastro-lirica-do-objecto/>

MÚSICA NEGATIVA

e. m. de melo e castro

1965
77

E. M. de Melo e Castro, *Música negativa*, performance, 1965-1977. Filme realizado por Ana Hatherly, 1977.

Fonte: Arquivo Digital da PO.EX. <https://po-ex.net/taxonomia/materialidades/videograficas/e-m-de-melocastro-musica-negativa/>

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Pierre Garnier

First International
Exhibition of **Concrete
& Kinetic Poetry**

St. Catharine's College
Rushmore Rooms,
Cambridge: Sat. Nov.
28th to Sat. Dec. 5th
10-5, entrance free

The exhibits are generally identified by the numbers given to the individual artists or groups in the catalogue. Enquire to the organisers, the International Kinetic Poetry Fund, for sales and bibliographic details.

- switzerland: 1. **eugen gomringer**, 33 konstellationen; die konstellationen 1953-1962.
- portugal: 2. **e.m. de melo e castro**, objecto de efeito progressivo; ideogramas.
3. **poesia experimental 1**, poems by antonio aragao, antonio baharona da fonseca, antonio ramos rosa, e.m. de melo e castro, heberto helder, salette tavares, luis de camoes, angelo de lima, mario cesariny de vasconcelos, emilio villa.
- venezuela: 4. **josé-maria cruxent**; métromane; versificateur; yupzkedgo; écritoscope.
- czechoslovakia: 5. **josef hirsal and bohumila grögerová**, mss of "job — boj" 1962.
6. **ladislav novák**, manuscripts; phonic poems.
- austria: 7. **heinz gappmayr**, zeichen; zeichen 2.
8. **ernst jandl**, laute und luise (manuscripts and tape); lange gedichte; klare gerührt (mss.).
9. **konrad bayer**, edited **edition 62**; der stein der weisen; starker toback (with oswald wiener).
- brazil: 10. **augusto de campos**, from **noigandres 4 & 5**; cubagramma; cidade.
11. **haroldo de campos**, from **noigandres 4 & 5**.
12. **décio pignatari**, from **noigandres 4 & 5**; semiotic poems.
13. **ronaldo azaredo**, from **noigandres 4 & 5**; semiotic poems.
14. **josé lino grünewald**, from **noigandres 5**.
15. **luiz ángelo pinto**, semiotic poems.
16. **pedro xisto**, manuscripts.
17. **edgard braga**
- sweden: 18. **mats g. bengtsson**, nutcracker.
19. **emil bengt johnson**, essäer om bror barsk; hyllningarna.
- france: 20. **pierre albert-birot**, grabinoulor.
21. **pierre garnier**, from **les lettres**; phonic poems: souffle manifeste, anthropologie, accélération, spatial.
22. **ilse garnier**, phonic poems: sprechaktionen 2, 3, 4, 5.
23. **henri chopin**, audio-poème from **cinquième saison**, revue-disque no. 20-21; pêche de nuit (film with luc peire and tjerk wicky).
24. **bernard heidsieck**, poème-partition b2 b3 (with record); poème-partition d 4p, from **cinquième saison**, no. 20-21; extracts from o-e, d 49.
25. **raoul hausmann**
26. **hans arp**, hans arp und die worte der dichter.
27. **nino calos**, light-mobile 1; light-mobile 2.
- italy: 28. **frank malina**, oui-no mobile. lent e.w. golding.
29. **john cage**, poem.
30. **fluxus group**, 4 issues fluxus newspapers; "an old pre-fluxus book" — an anthology; **george brecht**, water yam; games and puzzles; **robert watts**, complete works; **chieko shiomi**, events.
- u.s.a. 31. **brion gysin**, machine poems from **cinquième saison**, no. 20-21.
32. **paul de vree**, herfst (mss.); ode to ubac; pl. acid. amore; kleine caroli (tape).
33. **ivo michiels**, het boek alfa.
34. **freddy de vree**, mots pour karin; concrete novelette; propositions sur la nature.
35. **adriaan peel**, maandichten.
36. **patrick conrad**, ik lig in de dalai-lama.
37. **c.c. krijgelmans**, messiah.
37a. **dani franque**, concrete novel (mss.).
- japan: 38. **fujitomi yasuo**, the room keyed; something for august; accurate ambiguity; the magic house.
39. **seiichi niikuni**, zero-on (collected poems 1960-3).
- germany: 40. **max bense**, bestandteile des vorüber; entwurf einer rheinlandschaft; die präzisen vergnügen; aprèsfiche 1961 (see burkhardt); rosenschuttplatz.
41. **klaus burkhardt** (printer), affiche (nos. 16, 19, 21), aprèsfiche (see bense); feuilleton nos. 1-4 (dec. 1961 — aug. 1962); 4 post-cards; druck- und buchstabenbild; 4 posters; catalogue (pref. r. döhl = henri).
42. **reinhard döhl**, missa profana; portrait einwände (with k. burkhardt); fingerübungen; verlust der mitte (with günther c. kirchberger); fragment affiche no. 14; zwischenräume (anthology ed. r. döhl); 13 visuelle texte (ed. r. döhl).
43. **ludwig harig**, haiku hiroschima; zustand und veränderungen.
44. **hansjörg mayer** (printer), rosenschuttplatz (see bense); 13 visuelle texte (see döhl); rot 13 +.
45. **günther c. kirchberger** (painter), verlust der mitte (with r. döhl); catalogue 1961 (pref. h.

E. M. de Melo e Castro, *Roda lume*, p/b, som, 2'43", 1968 [RTP, 1969]. *Roda lume fogo*, videopoema [reconstrução], 1986.
Fonte: Arquivo Digital da PO.EX. <https://po-ex.net/taxonomia/materialidades/videograficas/e-m-de-melo-castro-roda-lume/>

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